

Make Your Data Work Twice

RSU

A Practical Guide to FAIR Research Data for Dental Researchers

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Uribe, S. (2026). Make Your Data Work Twice: A Practical Guide to FAIR Research Data for Dental Researchers. *Zenodo*.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19560667>

What You Will Learn

By the end of this lecture

After this lecture, you will be able to:

1. Explain why FAIR data matters for dental research
2. Set up a reproducible project folder structure
3. Learn about tools that will help you draw up a Data Management Plan: ARGOS or DMPTool
4. Separate data entry from data storage and analysis
5. Discover AMNESIA for anonymising research data
6. Generate a codebook with one R command
7. Package and publish your data in a repository with a DOI

FAIR Research Data

FAIR DATA PRINCIPLES

The Problem

Current state of dental research data

Uribe et al. 2022. J Dent Res 101;(11): 1307-1313

Of 7,509 dental articles analyzed (2016-2021):

Only 112 (1.5%) shared data

Average FAIR compliance: 32.6%

A Summary of FAIR levels by Year

B

Summary of FAIR levels by Journal

The Problem

Current state of dental research data

Uribe et al. 2022. J Dent Res 101;(11): 1307-1313

Of 7,509 dental articles analyzed (2016-2021):

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C

FAIR Maturity Indicator

What Machines See

The data gap in dental research

ML algorithms can process less than 1% of dental research data.

Most dental research data:

- Are not shared at all
- Are in proprietary formats (xlsx, sav)
- Lack metadata and documentation
- Cannot be found by machines

Your data is invisible to the future of science.

What You See

The screenshot shows the Zenodo interface for a dataset. At the top, there's a search bar and navigation links for 'Communities' and 'My dashboard'. A notification banner indicates a 'Planned intervention' on Thursday April 23rd. The dataset title is 'DATASET Clinical and Radiographic Evaluation Data of Autotransplantation using 3D Replicas', published on August 4, 2024. The authors are Lejnies, Mika (Researcher) and Uribe, Sergio E (Contact person). The description states: 'This dataset repository contains detailed data and analysis scripts related to a research study on autotransplantation using 3D replicas. The study aims to evaluate clinical outcomes and radiographic changes over time in dental autotransplantation cases. The dataset includes CSV files containing clinical data, detailed radiographic evaluation results, and HTML files documenting analysis procedures and findings.' The 'Files' section shows a file named '01_readme.md' with a preview of its content, including session information and matrix products. On the right, there are management buttons (Manage, Edit, New version, Share) and a statistics box showing 229 views and 441 downloads. Below that is a table of versions: Version v2 (10.5281/zenodo.13208598) and Version v1 (10.5281/zenodo.13199374).

What Machines See

```
8
9
10 <meta charset="utf-8">
11 <meta http-equiv="X-UA-Compatible" content="IE=edge">
12 <meta name="viewport" content="width=device-width, initial-scale=1">
13 <meta name="google-site-verification" content="5f9GCLl0wrv9090t01TadV7byEvFpCyK2VKS_s"/>
14 <meta name="google-site-verification" content="RpsZp84IKW-s11BpT0G87Z6XV60eozD5C3KTM-AiY4"/>
15
16
17 <meta name="generator" content="InvenioRDM 14.0"/>
18
19
20
21
22
23
24 <meta name="description" content="This dataset repository contains detailed data and analysis scripts related to a research study on autotransplantation using 3D replicas. The study aims to evaluate clinical outcomes and radiographic changes over time in dental autotransplantation cases. The dataset includes CSV files containing clinical data, detailed radiographic evaluation results, and HTML files documenting analysis procedures and findings." />
25 <meta name="citation_title" content="DATASET Clinical and Radiographic Evaluation Data of Autotransplantation using 3D Replicas" />
26 <meta name="citation_author" content="Lejnies, Mika" />
27 <meta name="citation_author" content="Uribe, Sergio E" />
28 <meta name="citation_doi" content="10.5281/zenodo.13208598" />
29 <meta name="citation_abstract_html_url" content="https://zenodo.org/records/13208598" />
30 <meta name="citation_abstract_html_url" content="https://zenodo.org/records/13208598" />
31 <meta name="og:title" content="DATASET Clinical and Radiographic Evaluation Data of Autotransplantation using 3D Replicas" />
32 <meta name="og:description" content="This dataset repository contains detailed data and analysis scripts related to a research study on autotransplantation using 3D replicas. The study aims to evaluate clinical outcomes and radiographic changes over time in dental autotransplantation cases. The dataset includes CSV files containing clinical data, detailed radiographic evaluation results, and HTML files documenting analysis procedures and findings." />
33 <meta name="og:url" content="https://zenodo.org/records/13208598" />
34 <meta name="og:site_name" content="Zenodo" />
35 <meta name="twitter:card" content="summary" />
36 <meta name="twitter:site" content="@zenodo.org" />
37 <meta name="twitter:title" content="DATASET Clinical and Radiographic Evaluation Data of Autotransplantation using 3D Replicas" />
38 <meta name="twitter:description" content="This dataset repository contains detailed data and analysis scripts related to a research study on autotransplantation using 3D replicas. The study aims to evaluate clinical outcomes and radiographic changes over time in dental autotransplantation cases. The dataset includes CSV files containing clinical data, detailed radiographic evaluation results, and HTML files documenting analysis procedures and findings." />
39
40 <link rel="alternate" type="application/octet-stream" href="https://zenodo.org/records/13208598/files/01_readme.md">
41 <link rel="item" type="application/octet-stream" href="https://zenodo.org/records/13208598/files/01_readme.md">
42
43 <link rel="alternate" type="text/csv" href="https://zenodo.org/records/13208598/files/DATA_04%20Final%20Results%20Autotransplantation%203d%20Replicas%20-%20CLINICAL%20DATA.csv">
44 <link rel="item" type="text/csv" href="https://zenodo.org/records/13208598/files/DATA_04%20Final%20Results%20Autotransplantation%203d%20Replicas%20-%20CLINICAL%20DATA.csv">
45
46 <link rel="alternate" type="text/html" href="https://zenodo.org/records/13208598/files/SCRIPT_02_radiographic_evaluation_miks_autotransplantation.html">
47 <link rel="item" type="text/html" href="https://zenodo.org/records/13208598/files/SCRIPT_02_radiographic_evaluation_miks_autotransplantation.html">
48
49 <link rel="alternate" type="text/html" href="https://zenodo.org/records/13208598/files/SCRIPT_03_clinical_evaluation_miks_autotransplantation.html">
50 <link rel="item" type="text/html" href="https://zenodo.org/records/13208598/files/SCRIPT_03_clinical_evaluation_miks_autotransplantation.html">
51
52 <link rel="alternate" type="text/csv" href="https://zenodo.org/records/13208598/files/DATA_01%20R%20pilot%20study%20calibrations%20data.csv">
53 <link rel="item" type="text/csv" href="https://zenodo.org/records/13208598/files/DATA_01%20R%20pilot%20study%20calibrations%20data.csv">
54
55 <link rel="alternate" type="text/csv" href="https://zenodo.org/records/13208598/files/DATA_02%20R%20pilot%20study%20calibrations%20data.csv">
56 <link rel="item" type="text/csv" href="https://zenodo.org/records/13208598/files/DATA_02%20R%20pilot%20study%20calibrations%20data.csv">
57
58 <link rel="alternate" type="text/csv" href="https://zenodo.org/records/13208598/files/DATA_03%20R%20pilot%20study%20calibrations%20data.csv">
59 <link rel="item" type="text/csv" href="https://zenodo.org/records/13208598/files/DATA_03%20R%20pilot%20study%20calibrations%20data.csv">
60
61 <link rel="alternate" type="text/html" href="https://zenodo.org/records/13208598/files/SCRIPT_01_pilot_calibration_radiographic_miks_autotransplantation.html">
62 <link rel="item" type="text/html" href="https://zenodo.org/records/13208598/files/SCRIPT_01_pilot_calibration_radiographic_miks_autotransplantation.html">
63
64 <link rel="alternate" type="text/csv" href="https://zenodo.org/records/13208598/files/DATA_05%20Final%20Results%20Autotransplantation%203d%20Replicas%20-%20CLINICAL%20DATA%20.csv">
65 <link rel="item" type="text/csv" href="https://zenodo.org/records/13208598/files/DATA_05%20Final%20Results%20Autotransplantation%203d%20Replicas%20-%20CLINICAL%20DATA%20.csv">
```


What Machines See

The Main Beneficiary

Your future self

Every new project starts where
the last one ended.

Good data management means you can:

- Reuse your own data and code
- Find your files months or years later
- Collaborate without confusion
- Submit to journals faster
- Respond to reviewers with confidence

Proper research data management today
will make your future self happier.

RSU

Step 1: Start with Your Question

The question defines everything

Question

Study Design

Data to Collect

Step 1: Start with Your Question

The question defines everything

The screenshot shows the Equator Network website. At the top left is the logo for Equator Network, which consists of a green sphere with a white line and the text "equator network". To the right of the logo is the tagline "Enhancing the QUALITY and Transparency Of health Research". Further right is a globe icon and a link for "Website translation help". Below the header is a navigation menu with links for Home, About us, Library, Toolkits, Courses & events, News, Blog, Librarian Network, and Contact. The main content area has a green banner with the text "Your one-stop-shop for writing and publishing high-impact health research" and a list of services: "find reporting guidelines | improve your writing | join our courses | run your own training course | enhance your peer review | implement guidelines". Below the banner are three main sections: "Library for health research reporting", "Reporting guidelines for main study types", and a "CONSORT" banner. The "Library for health research reporting" section includes a description of the library and four links: "Search for reporting guidelines", "Not sure which reporting guideline to use?", "Reporting guidelines under development", and "Visit the library for more resources". The "Reporting guidelines for main study types" section lists various study types and their corresponding reporting guidelines, such as "Randomised trials" with "CONSORT" and "Extensions", "Observational studies" with "STROBE" and "Extensions", "Systematic reviews" with "PRISMA" and "Extensions", "Study protocols" with "SPIRIT" and "PRISMA-P", "Diagnostic/prognostic studies" with "STARD" and "TRIPOD", "Case reports" with "CARE" and "Extensions", "Clinical practice guidelines" with "AGREE" and "RIGHT", "Qualitative research" with "SRQR" and "COREQ", "Animal pre-clinical studies" with "ARRIVE" and "Extensions", "Quality improvement studies" with "SQUIRE" and "Extensions", and "Economic evaluations" with "CHEERS" and "Extensions". At the bottom of this section is a link "See all 622 reporting guidelines". The "CONSORT" banner features an image of tools and a sign that says "Apologies! The CONSORT website is temporarily unavailable".

equator network Enhancing the **QUALITY** and **Transparency Of health Research** Website translation help

Home About us Library Toolkits Courses & events News Blog Librarian Network Contact

Your one-stop-shop for writing and publishing high-impact health research
find reporting guidelines | improve your writing | join our courses | run your own training course | enhance your peer review | implement guidelines

Library for health research reporting
The Library contains a comprehensive searchable database of reporting guidelines and also links to other resources relevant to research reporting.

- Search for reporting guidelines
- Not sure which reporting guideline to use?
- Reporting guidelines under development
- Visit the library for more resources

Reporting guidelines for main study types

Randomised trials	CONSORT	Extensions
Observational studies	STROBE	Extensions
Systematic reviews	PRISMA	Extensions
Study protocols	SPIRIT	PRISMA-P
Diagnostic/prognostic studies	STARD	TRIPOD
Case reports	CARE	Extensions
Clinical practice guidelines	AGREE	RIGHT
Qualitative research	SRQR	COREQ
Animal pre-clinical studies	ARRIVE	
Quality improvement studies	SQUIRE	Extensions
Economic evaluations	CHEERS	Extensions

[See all 622 reporting guidelines](#)

CONSORT The **CONSORT** website is temporarily unavailable

Step 2: Write Your Data Management Plan

Before you collect a single data point

Your DMP answers:

1. What data will you collect?
2. What format will you use?
3. Where will data be stored?
4. Who will have access?
5. When will you make data available?
6. What license will you apply?

Step 2: Write Your Data Management Plan

1.

Before you collect a single data point

Tools:

- ARGOS (argos.openaire.eu)
For Horizon and institutional projects
- DMPTool (dmptool.org)
For other research projects

Home

Public Plans

Public Descriptions

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Glossary User Guide

Public Plans > Research Data Management Plan (DMP) for EpiDentLatvia: ...

Plan

Research Data Management Plan (DMP) for EpiDentLatvia: Mapping the Epidemiological Profile of Oral Health in Latvian Children and Adolescents

Version 2

Finalized Edited: 8/20/25, 10:18 AM DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15313344

Main Info

Title of DMP Research Data Management Plan (DMP) for EpiDentLatvia: Mapping the Epidemiological Profile of Oral Health in Latvian Children and Adolescents

Description The Data Management Plan (DMP) for the EpiDentLatvia project describe the plan for managing, storing, sharing, and preserving data generated during the research. **EpiDentLatvia** targets the urgent oral health challenge in Latvia, where nearly all 12-year-olds are affected by dental caries. The project aims to generate evidence using traditional statistics and machine learning to identify risk factors, predict dental service needs and map inequalities in access. By analysing national and research datasets, it will inform policies that support prevention-focused, equitable dental care in line with WHO and UN health goals. The primary objectives of this DMP are:
1. **Data Collection and Standardisation:** Establishing protocols...

[show more](#)

Language English

Contact Sergio Uribe

Researchers Sergio Uribe (orcid:0000-0003-0684-2025), Ilze Maldupa (orcid:0000-0002-5967-956X)

Organizations Riga Stradiņš University

DOI provided

zenodo
10.5281/zenodo.15313344

Plan Authors

Sergio E. Uribe
Owner - All Sections

EpiDentLatvia **DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN**

WHAT **DATA** WILL YOU **COLLECT**?

REUSABLE EXISTING DATASETS:

National administrative health records, previous research datasets (ECC, GA, COVERAGE, COVID, YOUNG).

WHAT **FORMAT** WILL YOU **USE**?

CSV (Comma-Separated Values) for data files.

WHERE WILL **DATA** BE **STORED**?

RESEARCH: Secure, password-protected shared cloud folder.

LONG-TERM: RSU Dataverse and Institutional Repository.

WHO WILL HAVE **ACCESS**?

CURRENTLY: Restricted to Project Researchers (Urbe & Maldupa).

LATER: Open Access (anyone without restriction).

WHEN WILL YOU **MAKE** **DATA** **AVAILABLE**?

By 2025-12-31.

WHAT **LICENSE** WILL YOU **APPLY**?

**CREATIVE COMMONS ATTRIBUTION
SHARE-ALIKE 4.0 (CC-BY-SA 4.0).**

Riga Stradiņš University (rsu.lv)

Riga Stradiņš University (rsu.lv)

Create a new plan

Before you get started, we need some information about your research project to set you up with the best DMP template for your needs.

* What research project are you planning?

If applying for funding, state the project title exactly as in the proposal.

mock project for testing, practice, or educational purposes

* Select the primary research organization

Research organization

- or -

No research organization associated with this plan or my research organization is not listed

* Select the primary funding organization

Funder

- or -

No funder associated with this plan or my funder is not listed

Create plan

Cancel

Step 2: DMP + Protocol

The First Project Publication!

The screenshot displays the ISRCTN registry interface. At the top, the BMC logo (Part of Springer Nature) is visible. Below it, the 'ISRCTN registry' title is shown next to a search bar and an 'Advanced Search' link. A navigation menu includes options like 'View all studies', 'Why register?', 'Register your study', 'Update your record', 'Report your results', and 'Get help'. The main content area features the study ID 'ISRCTN17005348' with a DOI link, an 'Export as PDF' button, and social media icons. The study title is 'New non-invasive treatments for the control and treatment of early childhood caries'. A status summary table on the right lists various milestones with corresponding icons: Retrospectively registered (yellow checkmark), Protocol added (green checkmark), SAP not yet added (yellow question mark), Results added (green checkmark), Raw data added (green checkmark), and Study completed (blue checkmark).

Submission date 16/06/2021	Recruitment status No longer recruiting	Retrospectively registered
Registration date 30/06/2021	Overall study status Completed	Protocol added
Last edited 08/04/2024	Condition category Oral Health	SAP not yet added
		Results added
		Raw data added
		Study completed

RSU

Step 3: Set Up Your Project Folder

Use a standard structure for every project

```
project-name/  
  data/  
    raw/      (never touch)  
    processed/  
  scripts/  
  output/  
  docs/  
  README.md
```

R packages:

prodigenr: auto-creates folder scaffold
`prodigenr::setup_project('my-study')`

here: portable file paths

```
here::here('data', 'raw', 'file.csv')
```

Step 3: Set Up Your Project Folder

Use a standard structure for every project

Step 3: Set Up Your Project Folder

Use a standard structure for every project

prodigenr

Step 3: Set Up Your Project Folder

Naming Files

```
01_marshall-data.md
01_marshall-data.r
02_pre-dea-filtering.md
02_pre-dea-filtering.r
03_dea-with-limma-voom.md
03_dea-with-limma-voom.r
04_explore-dea-results.md
04_explore-dea-results.r
90_limma-model-term-name-fiasco.md
90_limma-model-term-name-fiasco.r
Makefile
figure
helper01_load-counts.r
helper02_load-exp-des.r
helper03_load-focus-statinf.r
helper04_extract-and-tidy.r
tmp.txt
```

```
01.md
01.r
02.md
02.r
03.md
03.r
04.md
04.r
90.md
90.r
Makefile
figure
helper01.r
helper02.r
helper03.r
helper04.r
tmp.txt
```

Step 3: Set Up Your Project Folder

Use a standard structure for every project

Name	Type
project draft.doc	Microsoft Word 9...
project draft1.doc	Microsoft Word 9...
project final.doc	Microsoft Word 9...
project final1.doc	Microsoft Word 9...
project final2.doc	Microsoft Word 9...
project FINAL final.doc	Microsoft Word 9...
project FINAL final1.doc	Microsoft Word 9...
project FINAL final2.doc	Microsoft Word 9...
project final THIS IS THE ONE TO SUBMIT.doc	Microsoft Word 9...
project final THIS IS THE ONE TO SUBMIT v2.doc	Microsoft Word 9...

Step 3: Set Up Your Project Folder History

Step 4: Collect Data with Forms

Separate entry from storage from analysis

Use forms for data entry: Google Forms, REDCap.

Export to CSV (not xlsx). Remember the Excel MARCH1 problem.

The Two Rules

1. Don't touch your raw data
2. Remember rule 1

Raw data is sacred.
All work happens on copies.

Export Format

Always export as CSV

- Open format
- Interoperable
- No auto-formatting
- Any software can read it

Step 4: Collect Data with Forms

Separate entry from storage from analysis

RSU

Step 5: Preserve Your Raw Data

One-way process:
entry to export

Workflow:

1. Collect data via form
2. Export as raw_data.csv
3. Set file to read-only
4. Copy for cleaning and analysis

Never edit the original export.

Data entry and data export is a one-way process.

Step 6: Anonymize Your Data

Remove personally identifiable information

Two types of identifiers:

Direct: name, national ID, email, phone

-> Remove entirely, replace with anonymous IDs

Quasi: age + sex + city combinations

-> One person from a small city = identifiable

-> Generalize: age groups, merge small cities

•R package: sdcMicro

•

•globalRecode(): age -> age groups

•groupAndRename(): merge small cities

•localSuppression(): suppress unique records

•addNoise(): mask exact numeric values

•report(): document all transformations

Privacy made simple. Data Anonymization.

Transform personal data into open statistical data in just a few simple steps.

Your Research. Your Data. Your Privacy.

[Learn more](#)

Amnesia allows all to effortlessly anonymize their data by providing formal privacy guarantees.

Amnesia features a user - friendly interface, supports a wide range of data formats, and ensures that the resulting anonymized datasets are no longer classified as personal data under the GDPR.

Step 6: Anonymize Your Data

Remove personally identifiable information

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	
1	patient_name	national_id	email	phone	age	sex	municipality	education	dmft	cpi_max	monthly_income	
2	Jānis Bērziņš	PK-922904	patient1@inbox.lv	+371 24615972	23	F	Riga	University	5	0	1200	
3	Anna Kalniņa	PK-118725	patient2@inbox.lv	+371 24081250	45	M	Cesis	Secondary	12	2	850	
4	Marta Ozoliņa	PK-888078	patient3@inbox.lv	+371 21748802	67	F	Riga	University	18	3	1500	
5	Pēteris Liepiņš	PK-811787	patient4@inbox.lv	+371 24961443	34	M	Jelgava	Primary	3	1	620	
6	Ilze Krūmiņa	PK-334671	patient5@inbox.lv	+371 21516081	28	F	Riga	University	2	0	1800	
7	Kārlis Vanags	PK-407486	patient6@inbox.lv	+371 25288684	72	M	Cesis	Secondary	22	4	540	
8	Dace Rubene	PK-876505	patient7@inbox.lv	+371 26366504	41	F	Jelgava	University	7	2	1100	
9	Andris Zariņš	PK-188919	patient8@inbox.lv	+371 24224445	55	M	Riga	Secondary	14	3	950	
10	Līga Feldmane	PK-231150	patient9@inbox.lv	+371 27612292	29	F	Cesis	University	1	0	1650	
11	Toms Balodis	PK-887565	patient10@inbox.lv	+371 25396351	38	M	Riga	Primary	8	1	700	
12	Elīna Vītola	PK-122507	patient11@inbox.lv	+371 27190864	62	F	Ventspils	Secondary	16	3	780	
13	Rihards Grants	PK-693845	patient12@inbox.lv	+371 29890760	47	M	Riga	University	9	2	1300	
14	Signe Jansone	PK-177693	patient13@inbox.lv	+371 24988380	31	F	Riga	University	4	1	1400	
15	Mikus Celmiņš	PK-174716	patient14@inbox.lv	+371 27874725	26	M	Ventspils	Secondary	3	0	600	
16	Zane Kovaļevs	PK-401579	patient15@inbox.lv	+371 23029134	69	F	Cesis	Primary	19	4	490	
17												
18												

Step 6: Anonymize Your Data

Remove personally identifiable information

The screenshot displays the Amnesia Dashboard interface. On the left is a dark sidebar with the Amnesia logo and a navigation menu. The main content area is light gray and contains two buttons at the top: "Upload sensitive data" and "Upload DICOM Images". Below these is a large upload area with a file named "dental_survey" (1.4 KIB) and an "Upload" button in the top right corner. A warning message at the top right states: "Do not upload sensitive data, the online edition is for demonstration purposes only".

Amnesia Dashboard
version:1.4.0 beta

Do not upload sensitive data, the online edition is for demonstration purposes only

Upload sensitive data Upload DICOM Images

dental_survey
1.4 KIB

Upload

amnesia

- Anonymization Wizard
- Reset
- Source
- Anonymized
- Hierarchy
- Algorithms
- Solution Graph
- Results
- Back to Amnesia website

Step 6: Anonymize Your Data

Remove personally identifiable information

Amnesia

- Anonymization Wizard
- Reset
- Source
 - Manage
 - Load From Local Disk
 - Load From Zenodo
 - Load From Dataverse Server
- Anonymized
- Hierarchy
- Algorithms
- Solution Graph
- Results
- Back to Amnesia website

Dataset Load

1. Delimiters & Dataset type

2. Attributes

Select the delimiters and the dataset type

Dataset preview

patient_name,national_id,email,phone,age,sex,municipality,education,dmft,cpi_max,monthly_income

Jānis Bērziņš,PK-922904,patient1@inbox.lv,+371 24615972,23,F,Rīga,University,5,0,1200

Anna Kalniņa,PK-118725,patient2@inbox.lv,+371 24081250,45,M,Cēsis,Secondary,12,2,850

Marta Ozoliņa,PK-888078,patient3@inbox.lv,+371 21748802,67,F,Rīga,University,18,3,1500

...

Delimiter *

,

Dataset type :

Simple table

Previous

Next

Cancel

Step 6: Anonymize Your Data

Remove personally identifiable information

Amnesia

- Anonymization Wizard
- Reset
- Source
 - Manage
 - Load From Local Disk
 - Load From Zenodo
 - Load From Dataverse Server
- Anonymized
- Hierarchy
- Algorithms
- Solution Graph
- Results
- Back to Amnesia website

Amnesia Anonymization Tool
version:1.4.0 beta

Do not upload sensitive data, the online edition is for demonstration purposes only

Dataset Load

1. Delimiters & Dataset type

2. Attributes

Choose the attributes and their types

Select All

Select the attributes to include in the output dataset and assign a type to each attribute.

patient_name	national_id	email	phone	age	sex	municipality	education	dmft	cpi_max	monthly_income
string	string	string	string	int	string	string	string	int	int	int
Anna Kalniņa	PK-118725	patient2@inbox.lv	+371 24081250	45	M	Cesis	Secondary	12	2	850
Marta Ozoliņa	PK-888078	patient3@inbox.lv	+371 21748802	67	F	Riga	University	18	3	1500
Pēteris Liepiņš	PK-811787	patient4@inbox.lv	+371 24961443	34	M	Jelgava	Primary	3	1	620
Ilze Krūmiņa	PK-334671	patient5@inbox.lv	+371 21516081	28	F	Riga	University	2	0	1800
Kārlis Vanags	PK-407486	patient6@inbox.lv	+371 25288684	72	M	Cesis	Secondary	22	4	540

Previous Finish Cancel

© 2022. All Rights Reserved.

Step 6: Anonymize Your Data

Remove personally identifiable information

Amnesia Anonymization Tool
version:1.4.0 beta

Pre-Anonymization Process

Show 10 entries

age	sex	municipality	education	dmft	cpi_max	monthly_income
23	F	Jelgava	Primary	5	0	1200
45	M	Riga	University	12	2	850
67	F	Cesis	Secondary	18	3	1500
34	M	Jelgava	University	3	1	620
28	F	Riga	Secondary	2	0	1800
72	M	Jelgava	University	22	4	540
41	F	Riga	Secondary	7	2	1100
55	M	Cesis	University	14	3	950
29	F	Riga	Primary	1	0	1650
38	M	Riga	Primary	8	1	700

Showing 1 to 10 of 15 entries

Previous 1 2 Next

Close Check

Anonymization Check Proceed to Hierarchies

Step 7: Analyze in R

Your script IS your analysis documentation

Why R? Open source, reproducible, largest package ecosystem.

Your R script documents every step from raw data to results.

Dataset

```
# 2. Load and prepare the data
# For this example, we'll use the built-in mtcars dataset
data <- mtcars %>%
  as_tibble() %>%
  select(mpg, hp, wt)
```

Data split

```
# 3. Split the data
set.seed(123)
data_split <- initial_split(data, prop = 0.75)
train_data <- training(data_split)
test_data <- testing(data_split)
```

The model

```
# 4. Create and train the model
lm_model <- linear_reg() %>%
  set_engine("lm") %>%
  fit(mpg ~ hp + wt, data = train_data)
```

Model evaluation

```
# 5. Evaluate the model
predictions <- lm_model %>%
  predict(test_data) %>%
```

Table of contents

- Packages
- Dataset**
- Data split
- The model
- Model evaluation
- Multicollinearity
- Compare to baseline model

Step 8: Generate Your Codebook

One command in R

```
dataMaid::makeDataReport(your_data)
```

This produces a document describing every variable:

- Variable name and type
- Summary statistics
- Distribution plots
- Missing values
- Potential errors flagged

The codebook answers:

Who created the data

What each variable means

How it was collected

When and where it was generated

Step 8: Generate Your Codebook

One command in R

```
---  
title: "Data Codebook Example with dataMaid"  
author: "Your Name"  
format:  
  html:  
    toc: true  
    code-fold: true  
  pdf:  
    toc: true  
execute:  
  echo: true  
  warning: false  
  message: false  
---
```

```
{r}   
#| label: setup  
#| include: false  
  
# Install if needed (uncomment first time)  
# install.packages("dataMaid")  
  
library(dataMaid)  
library(knitr)
```

```
∨ {r}   
# Load example data from dataMaid  
data(toyData)  
  
makeCodebook(  
  toyData,  
  reportTitle = "Codebook for toyData (dataMaid example)",  
  file = "toydata_codebook.Rmd",  
  replace = TRUE  
)
```

Step 8: Generate Your Codebook

One command in R

Codebook for toyData (dataMaid example)

Autogenerated data summary from dataMaid

2026-04-13 23:22:34

Data report overview

The dataset examined has the following dimensions:

Feature	Result
Number of observations	15
Number of variables	6

Codebook summary table

Label	Variable	Class	# unique values	Missing	Description
	pill	factor	3	13.33 %	
	events	numeric	9	20.00 %	
	region	factor	7	0.00 %	
	change	numeric	15	0.00 %	
	id	factor	15	0.00 %	
	spotifysong	factor	1	0.00 %	

Variable list

pill

Feature	Result
Variable type	factor
Number of missing obs.	2 (13.33 %)
Number of unique values	2
Mode	"red"
Reference category	blue

- Observed factor levels: "blue", "red".

RSU

Step 9: Package Everything

Create a complete, self-contained data package

Create a zip file containing:

README.md

Plain language description of the project

raw_data.csv

Anonymized raw data in CSV format

analysis_script.R (or .qmd)

Complete analysis code

Also include:

codebook.pdf

Generated by dataMaid

LICENSE

Recommend CC-BY 4.0 for data

Step 9: Package Everything

Create a complete, self-contained data package

Step 10: Publish and Cite

Upload before submitting your manuscript

General repositories:

Zenodo (zenodo.org)

Automatic DOI, metadata, versioning
Hosted by CERN, free, reliable

Institutional repositories:

RSU Dataverse

Or your university's own repository

How to publish:

1. Upload your zip file
2. Fill in metadata fields
3. Choose access level:
open / restricted / embargoed
4. Get your DOI
5. Add DOI to your manuscript

Tip: Upload data BEFORE submitting the paper.

Step 10: Publish and Cite

Upload before submitting your manuscript

DataverseLV

Guide News ▾ About project Repository ▾ English ▾

Latvian research data repository and data stewards network

The DataverseLV repository is a secure platform for long-term preservation and publication of research data.

In addition to the repository, the DataverseLV website also provides useful information on research data management and the support offered by the Latvian data stewards network.

Repository

RSU

Cite Your Data

Data as a citable
product of research

In your manuscript:

Data Availability Statement:

'The data and R analysis script that support the findings of this study are available in the Zenodo repository:

doi:10.5281/zenodo.XXXXXXX'

In your reference list:

Author(s). (Year). Dataset title [Data set].

Repository. <https://doi.org/XX.XXXX/XXXXXXXX>

Your data gets its own DOI and citation count.

Cite Your Data

Data as a citable product of research

Received: 25 July 2023 | Revised: 15 February 2024 | Accepted: 18 March 2024

DOI: 10.1111/eje.13009

ORIGINAL ARTICLE

WILEY

Artificial intelligence chatbots and large language models in dental education: Worldwide survey of educators

Sergio E. Uribe^{1,2,3,4} | Ilze Maldupa¹ | Argyro Kavadella⁵ | Maha El Tantawi⁶ | Akhilanand Chaurasia^{4,7} | Margherita Fontana⁸ | Rodrigo Marino⁹ | Nicola Innes¹⁰ | Falk Schwendicke^{4,11}

2 | MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 | Design and Ethics

This cross-sectional study, conducted via an online survey in May–June 2023, focused on gathering data from dental educators worldwide using a convenience sampling approach. The report follows the recommendations for Internet E-Surveys Reporting Guidelines (CHERRIES)¹⁶ (see Table S1). The study protocol was approved by the Ethical Committee of Riga Stradins University (2-PĒK-4/372/2023) and is available at <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/5FESK>. Before participation, online informed consent was gathered, where participants were briefed about the survey length, data storage practices, investigator details, and study purpose. IP checks were performed to protect participant data to avoid multiple submissions from the same user. Only aggregated, anonymised data were used in the analysis.

DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

The data and analysis scripts supporting this research's results are available here: Uribe, Sergio & Maldupa, Ilze. Worldwide Survey on the Impact of AI Chatbots and Large Language Models in Dental Education: Insights from Dental Educators [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8074534>

Planned intervention: On Thursday April 23rd 06:30 UTC Zenodo will be unavailable for 20-30 minutes to perform a storage cluster upgrade.

Baltic Biomaterials Centre of Excellence
Part of EU Open Research Repository

Published June 23, 2023 | Version v1

Dataset

Dataset Worldwide Survey on the Impact of AI Chatbots and Large Language Models in Dental Education: Insights from Dental Educators

Uribe, Sergio¹ ; Maldupa, Ilze¹

Show affiliations

This dataset contains responses from participants regarding their awareness, knowledge, and perceptions of AI-powered tools in dental education. The data was collected during May-June 2023 to investigate the potential enhancement that AI can bring to dental education. The dataset includes variables related to participants' demographics, experiences, perceptions, and opinions.

Details in the published protocol by Uribe, S. E., & Maldupa, I. (2023, June 2). Chatbots In Dental Education - Research Protocol. <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/3BSG2>

Files

Name	Size	
00_README.pdf		
Files (738.1 kB)		
00_README.pdf md5:705877a2f14dc3415aec1a04393f12b	85.8 kB	
01_Dataset_Metadata.pdf md5:c8f6573befc13ce5ea648ba8956d0f79	134.5 kB	
02_codebook.pdf md5:04898b008191c3d8281e51499617224e	273.8 kB	
03_anon_df.csv md5:63f47896dd8fac89574bd71b7c3bb7d4	244.0 kB	

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10.5281/zenodo.8074534

Cite all versions? You can cite all versions by using the DOI 10.5281/zenodo.8074533. This DOI represents all versions, and will always resolve to the latest one. [Read more.](#)

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Keywords and subjects

chatbots chatGPT dental education

education technology Large Language Models

The 10 Steps

Your complete FAIR
data workflow

PLAN

1. Start with your research question
2. Write your Data Management Plan
3. Set up your project folder

COLLECT

4. Collect data with forms (not Excel)
5. Preserve your raw data untouched

PROCESS

6. Anonymize with sdcMicro
7. Analyze in R (script = documentation)
8. Generate codebook with dataMaid

SHARE

9. Package: README + data + code + codebook
10. Publish in Zenodo/Dataverse and cite

What Can You Do Today?

Pick one action. Do it this week.

Start your next project with a DMP using ARGOS or DMPTool.

Switch from Excel to forms + CSV for your data collection.

Quick Win

Add a README.md to one existing project folder

Use `janitor::clean_names()` on your current dataset

Set your raw data file to read-only today

Next Step

Upload one dataset to Zenodo this month

Generate a codebook with `dataMaid::makeDataReport()`

Share your R script alongside your next manuscript

Resources

Tools and references

DMP Tools:

ARGOS: argos.openaire.eu

DMPTool: dmptool.org

Repositories:

Zenodo: zenodo.org

RSU Dataverse: dataverse.rsu.lv

Reference:

Uribe et al. *J Dent Res* 2022;101(11):1307-13

doi:10.1177/00220345221101321

R Packages:

tidyverse, janitor, skimr

gtsummary, dataMaid

here, pacman

prodigenr, quarto

FAIR Principles:

go-fair.org

fairsharing.org

Slides

Uribe, S. (2026). Make Your Data Work Twice: A Practical Guide to FAIR Research Data for Dental Researchers. *Zenodo*.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19560667>

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